

Bayesian Regional Climate Model Emulator with Spatially Varying Variable Selection

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Abstract. Regional Climate Models (RCM) provide high-resolution climate simulations that are important to investigate variation in regional scale projections. We introduce a Bayesian statistical framework to emulate RCM output variables using output variables from Global Circulation Models (GCM) as covariates. This emulator is an alternative to the RCM runs, which are computationally expensive. The Bayesian RCM emulator has spatially varying coefficients with data-dependent priors to perform variable selection in each location. To that end, we model both the spatially varying coefficients and the response as smooth spatial processes. The method is then applied to emulate precipitation from the CRCM regional model output from the North American Regional Climate Change Assessment Program (NARCCAP) using a set of variables from the CCSM global circulation model output. Furthermore, the prior weights are used to assess the usefulness of each covariate from the global model output, to emulate the regional model for each location of the NARCCAP data domain. We built the model on Summer data from 1970 to 1998 over a spatial domain covering the Western part of the continental United States and Canada and validate it with data from 1999-2000 over the same spatial domain.

1 Introduction

General Circulation Models (GCM) describe the large scale global atmospheric and oceanic dynamics. Computational constraints require coarse resolutions, and so GCMs provide limited information about regional scales. Regional Climate Models (RCM) can serve as dynamic downscaling models that use atmospheric interactions in the GCM to develop a higher resolution output, which is influenced by a smaller scale of topographical features (Yuqing et al. (2004)). Down-

scaling is used for interpolating low resolution variables to a higher resolution using predictor variables, under the assumption that “relationships can be established between atmospheric processes occurring at disparate temporal and/or spatial scales” (Wilby and Wigley (1997)). RCMs are useful for describing regional climate as well as for serving as an input for weather prediction models. However, as Wilby et al. (2000) state “RCMs are computationally demanding and require orders of magnitude more computer time than statistical downscaling to compute equivalent scenarios”. Since climate models are simulators of the physical climate system (O’Hagan (2006)), we define an RCM statistical emulator as a statistical downscaling model for GCMs.

The North American Regional Climate Change Assessment Program (NARCCAP) is an international program that has as a main goal of generating climate scenarios for use in impacts research. (Mearns et al. (2009)). They have proposed and applied a dynamical downscaling technique that consists of embedding RCMs within GCMs to obtain higher resolution evaluations of the climate model over the domain of interest, using different combinations of RCMs and GCMs. Since this dynamical downscaling technique is computationally expensive, a fast approximation to perform sensitivity analysis or for making informed prior judgements relating the GCM drivers for an RCM is of high value.

In this paper, we propose a statistical emulator of regional climate model output variables driven by GCM output variables. Our goal is to be able to use the GCM output to emulate the RCM output accurately, and to determine which set of variables from the GCM is the best possible combination to describe the RCM, depending on the location. To this end, we develop a spatially varying Bayesian model with data-dependent weights for each covariate that also varies over space. We address the following challenges: (1) an association between response and covariates that varies over space,

and hence a need to perform spatially varying variable selection, (2) a spatially smooth response, (3) a heavy computational burden given that the number of observations is big in this case, and (4) a need for a relatively fast emulation of the downscaling process. We use radial basis functions to represent and efficiently approximate the spatially varying regression coefficients, the BIC approximation for the Bayes factors used to estimate the data-dependent weights for each covariate in each location, and Vecchia's approach to approximate the likelihood in the posterior sampling steps.

Previous work on statistical emulators from Castruccio et al. (2014), Overstall and Woods (2016) and O'Hagan (2006) are concentrated on climate models projections and on computer experiment output, but to our knowledge, there is no previous work on regional climate model statistical emulators. The novelty of this work is twofold: first, we develop a spatially varying variable selection procedure useful for smooth model output statistics (MOS) that uses approximations to make it computationally efficient. Second, in terms of the application, our model can be used as a fast approximation of the RCM to emulate new scenarios in the RCM locations, given new values of covariates, and also to evaluate the relative importance of each combination of GCM output variables to describe RCM output. We show how our variable selection approach improves the statistical emulator performance, since it takes into account the uncertainty of the model selection (i.e. which set of covariates are included) using model averaging weights per location, and also models the spatial process for each coefficient and the response variable, separately.

The remainder of this paper is divided into five sections. The second section presents the NARCCAP data, and the selection of covariates from GCMs and RCMs. Next, a third section presents the statistical methods used in this paper while the fourth section presents a numerical simulation to demonstrate its properties. The fifth section outlines the data analysis for the NARCCAP data and the last section closes with a discussion of the results.

2 Data

Our main source of data is NARCCAP (Mearns et al. (2007)). Our data set consists of a response variable from the Canadian Regional Climate Model (CRCM) (Caya et al. (1995)) and seven covariates from the Community Climate System Model (CCSM), which is the global model embedded in the CRCM. The complete data sets can be accessed through: <https://www.earthsystemgrid.org/project/NARCCAP.html>. The two climate models have different resolutions and projections, as presented in Figure 1.

The global model resolution (256×128 grid boxes across the globe) was subsetted to create a grid box system covering North America and consisting of 83×33 grid boxes with the latitude and longitude of the global variable at the center.

Figure 1. Coordinates for the Canadian Regional Climate Model (CRCM) and the Community Climate System Model (CCSM) in the North American Region. The area outlined in red is the selected domain for the analysis in Section 5.

Figure 2. Response variable from the CRCM output and temperature (TREFHT) from the CCSM output.

Figure 2 presents the contrast between the spatial resolution from the response variable (RCM output) and that from the covariates (GCM output). Lastly, we choose to work with the Western part of North America, given that the region has a diverse topography, in terms of vegetation, climate and elevation (as shown in Figure 3).

The response variable is surface precipitation from the CRCM Regional Model, measured in kgm^2/s . Precipitation is usually presented in terms of mm, but we choose keep the

Table 1. Descriptive statistics for the covariates.

	log(PR)	PSL	TREFHT	OMEGA (510.45)	U (266.48)	V (266.48)	Qbot
Units	kgm^2/s		K	Pa/s	m/s	m/s	-
Min.	-13.82	100.949	273	-0.07888	-4.51	-7.540	-14.796
1st Qu.	-12.20	101.399	287	-0.00963	10.04	0.557	-3.972
Median	-11.56	101.551	291	0.00732	15.12	3.762	-0.704
Mean	-11.62	101.674	292	0.01255	14.55	3.718	-1.664
3rd Qu.	-10.94	101.882	296	0.03098	19.44	6.660	0.448
Max.	-8.91	103.057	305	0.11237	32.57	16.438	7.481

Figure 3. Elevation in meters in the North American Region. This variable was used as a driver to generate CRCM output, and although we do not include it in our model, it is highly correlated with several of the covariates we use over the domain of interest.

model units and also to transform the response variable using a log scale, to improve normal assumption. We use several variables from the CCSM global model as covariates. Three of them are surface variables: sea level pressure (PSL) measured in Pa, reference height temperature (TREFHT) measured in K, and atmospheric specific humidity (QBOT); we use vertical velocity (OMEGA) measured in Pa/s, that represents a mid altitude variable (measured at 510.45 hPa), and lastly, we use two variables measured in the jet level winds: wind east-west (U) and wind north-south (V) both measured in m/s at 267 hPa. We average the daily data over the Summer periods (Jun 1, 1970 through Aug 31, 1999) in the following way:

$$X_{kt}(s_i) = \frac{1}{91} \sum_{d=d_1}^{d_2} X_{ktd}(s_i)$$

for each covariate k in location s_i , where $d_1 = 152$ and $d_2 = 152 + 91 - 1$ are the first and last days of the Summer for each year t , respectively. In the same way $Y_t(s_i) = \sum_{d=d_1}^{d_2} Y_{td}(s_i)$ for the response variable.

Our data consist of observations for $T = 30$ years, $N = 5,200$ locations, and $P = 6$ covariates: PSL, TREFHT, QBOT, OMEGA, U500, and V500.

3 Statistical Model

Let $Y_t(s)$ be RCM model output for location s from the RCM resolution and year t . We model $Y_t(s)$ as:

$$Y_t(s) = \mu_t(s) + \varepsilon_t(s), \quad (1)$$

where $\varepsilon_t \sim GP(0, C(h, \Omega))$ and $C(h, \Omega)$ is the spatial covariance function that describes the smooth spatial process

using distance h and a set of parameters Ω . We assume independence in time, although it could be incorporated into the structure of ε . We write $\mu_t(s)$ as:

$$\mu_t(s) = \sum_{k=0}^p X_{kt}(s) \beta_k(s), \quad \text{with} \quad (2)$$

$$\beta_k(s) = v_k(s) f_k(s) = v_k(s) \sum_{j=1}^J \alpha_{kj} F_j(s) \quad (3)$$

where $X_{kt}(s)$ contains the GCM output data on predictor k at time t in each location from GCM grid box containing s from the regional model (RCM), and $X_{0t}(s) = 1$. Note that $X_{kt}(s)$ has the same value in all the RCM locations s that are included in the same GCM gridbox.

Define matrix Φ to have entries $\Phi_{ii'} = \phi(s_i - s_{i'})$ where $\phi(|s_i - s_{i'}|) = |s_i - s_{i'}|^2 \log |s_i - s_{i'}| / \eta$, and η is a scale parameter, making ϕ a thin plate spline basis function. We use spectral value decomposition to write $\Phi = UDU^T$, where D is diagonal and U contains the respective J eigenfunctions ordered by eigenvalue magnitude and evaluated at each location s_i . Let U_j be the j th eigenvector of Φ and $F_j(s_i)$ be the i th element of U_j . The advantages of thin-plate splines have to do with its flexibility to represent a myriad of spatial patterns given its piecewise smooth nature, as an alternative to the Gaussian radial basis that are infinitely smooth (Buhmann (2003)).

Let $\log(v_k) \sim GP(a_k, \Sigma_v)$, the vector v_k of length N has a multivariate log normal smooth prior centered in the observed mean of the log weights, and a covariance matrix Σ_v ; while α is a vector of coefficients to estimate, where each has a prior distribution $\alpha_{kj} \sim N(0, \sigma_b^2 \lambda_j^2)$, where λ_j is the j eigenvalue of the matrix constructed using radial basis functions. In this case, λ_j can help to regularize the number of eigenfunctions used, since the value is decreasing and it approaches to zero when j increases.

3.1 Estimation

Sampling $v_k(s)$ and α_{kj} is computationally expensive when the number of locations is big. Thus, in this section we describe a method for pre-estimating $v_k(s)$. We assume v_k , λ_j and F as pre-defined data-dependent quantities, thus the parameters to estimate in our model are only α_{kj} , σ_b^2 , and the set of parameters Ω . In order to estimate the pre-defined data-based weights, we use ideas of Bayesian model averaging (BMA). BMA was first proposed by Raftery et al. (1997) to account for model uncertainty by taking a weighted average of estimations coming from different models over a given model space. In this context, we call each of the 2^p possible combination of covariates a model structure M_ℓ and write the marginal posterior probability for the coefficient β in location s for covariate k as:

$$p(\beta|Y, X) = \sum_{\ell=1}^L p(\beta|M_\ell, Y, X) p(M_\ell|Y, X) \quad (4)$$

where $p(\beta|M_\ell, Y, X)$ is the likelihood of β given the model specification M_ℓ and the observed data $\{Y, X\}$, and $p(M_\ell|Y, X)$ is the model probability given the observed data, or in other words, a weight that reflects the model M_ℓ goodness-of-fit provided the observed data. Hoeting et al. (2000) show that there is a straight relationship between the posterior model probability and the Bayes factor, and Kass and Raftery (1995) proved that BIC can be used to approximate the same quantity via Bayes factors. In this work, we use the BIC to approximate the posterior model probability $\hat{p}(M_\ell|Y, X)$, and write the weight for variable k being included in the model as:

$$w_k = \sum_{\ell \in \{i: \beta_k \neq 0 \text{ in } M_i\}} p(M_\ell|Y, X) = \frac{BF_{M_\ell}}{\sum_h (BF_{M_h})} \quad (5)$$

where $BF_{M_\ell} = \exp(-0.5BIC_{M_\ell})$.

We use the BMA package (Raftery et al. (2015)) to estimate $w_k(s)$ in each location and after that, we smooth each of the k fields applying a simple local smoothing to $w_k(s)$, where we average the 5 closest observations (neighborhood \mathcal{N}_s) to obtain:

$$v_k(s) = \frac{1}{5} \sum_{s' \in \mathcal{N}_s} w_k(s') \quad (6)$$

We represent the coordinates of the observations using radial basis functions and spectral decomposition, and then calculate $F_j(s)$ and λ_j , that we use to plug in our model.

After obtaining all the pre-defined quantities, we perform a MCMC sampling scheme to estimate the posterior distribution. The covariance function for the first layer of the hierarchical model is specified as exponential, and thus include two parameters: $\Omega = \{\sigma_\varepsilon^2, \phi\}$. The hyper-priors are defined as: $\sigma_b^2 \sim IG(b, c)$, $\sigma_\varepsilon^2 \sim IG(d, e)$ and $\phi \sim U(0, R)$. We use Gibbs sampling for σ_b^2 and σ_ε^2 and rejection sampling for all of the other parameters: $\alpha_{k,j}$ and ϕ . In order to evaluate the likelihood of Y in each MCMC iteration, we use Vecchia's approximation (Vecchia (1988)) as specified by Guinness (2016), to speed up the computation. The quantities b, c, d, e, R are fixed to have noninformative priors for σ_b and σ_ε and we use R to set a limit on the maximum range for the exponential covariance function.

3.1.1 Vecchia's approximation

Vecchia's approximation (Vecchia (1988)) is a way to reduce the computing time and physical memory needed to evaluate a likelihood function. Let $Y \sim N(\mu, \Sigma_\theta)$ where Σ_θ is a matrix with entries determined by a covariate function K . The cost of evaluating the likelihood is in $\mathcal{O}(n^3)$ flops and the memory consumption is in $\mathcal{O}(n^2)$. If we have a permutation of the integers $1 : n$ $\tau : \{1, \dots, n\} \rightarrow \{1, \dots, n\}$ and a permuted vector y^τ where $y_i^\tau = y_{\tau(i)}$, then we can write the

likelihood as:

$$p_\theta(y_i, \dots, y_n) = p_\theta(y_1^\tau) \prod_{i=2}^n p_\theta(y_i^\tau | y_1^\tau, \dots, y_{i-1}^\tau). \quad (7)$$

Vecchia's approximation is:

$$p_{\theta, \tau, J}(y_i, \dots, y_n) = p_\theta(y_1^\tau) \prod_{i=2}^n p_\theta(y_i^\tau | y_{j_{i1}}^\tau, \dots, y_{j_{im_i}}^\tau) \quad (8)$$

where j_{i1}, \dots, j_{im_i} is an increasing sequence of integers between 1 and $i-1$, and $y_{j_{i1}}^\tau, \dots, y_{j_{im_i}}^\tau$ is a subset of $y_1^\tau, \dots, y_{i-1}^\tau$. The maximum minimum distance permutation was shown to provide good approximations when nearest neighbor conditioning sets were used. Guinness (2016) also provided an algorithm for grouping components of the likelihood approximation to increase speed and accuracy. We use this approximation to make the MCMC sampling from our emulator more computationally efficient.

4 Simulation Study

We study the performance of our model when estimating the spatially varying regression coefficients compared to a model that assumes the weights $v_k(s)$ are constant. Our main focus is to describe the ability of our model to estimate the coefficients accurately; thus we compare performance for varying degrees of spatial correlation in the weights, generating three different settings. For that, we use the MSE, the median absolute deviation (MAD) and the coverage for the coefficients $\beta_k(s) = v_k(s) f_k(s)$ in space.

We generate one set of $f_k(s)$ per simulation and 3 sets of $v_k(s)$ under different conditions, to have 3 settings as a result. In all settings we use a 10×10 spatial grid, with $N = 100$ locations and generate data for X_k with $k = 1, 2, \dots, 5$, each with a normal distribution $X_k \sim N(0, 2^{(1/k)})$ with $T = 12$ observations. Since the number of covariates is $p = 4$ the total number of possible models is $L = 2^p = 16$.

The set of $f_k(s)$ is generated as 4 independent spatially varying fields per simulation. Each of them is generated using a Matérn covariance function with different parameter values, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Example of $p = 4$ fields for $f_k(s)$.

The three options to generate $v_k(s)$ are (1) $v_k(s) = 1$ for all s and k , (2) chessboard surfaces of $v_k(s)$ divided into 4 blocks that differ according to the covariate k , and (3) smooth

Figure 5. Chessboard and Smooth settings for $v_k(s)$, with $k = 1, 2, 3, 4$.

Table 2. Six settings with their respective sets for $v_k(s)$ and Y .

$Y \sim GP(\mu, \Sigma)$	$v_k(s)$	Scenarios
$\Sigma = \sigma_\epsilon^2 * I$	Constant	Setting 1
	Chessboard	Setting 2
	Smooth	Setting 3
Σ exponential	Constant	Setting 4
	Chessboard	Setting 5
	Smooth	Setting 6

surfaces that range from 0 to 1. For the chessboard case covariate $k = 1$ has weights of 0.5 in each of the Northwest and Southeast corners, covariate $k = 2$ has weights of 0.5 in each of the Northeast and Southwest corners, and covariates $k = 3$ and 4 have weights of 0.25 on the South and North blocks respectively. For clarity, Figure 5 present spatial designs for $v_k(s)$, with $k = 1, 2, 3, 4$.

Then, we use the set of $f_k(s)$ and the two sets of $v_k(s)$, to have six combinations for $\beta_k(s) = f_k(s)v_k(s)$ and calculate $\mu_t(s) = \sum_{k=0}^p X_{tk}\beta_k(s)$ for each. We use $\mu_t(s)$ to generate random samples of $Y_t(s)$ using two options: one from a normal distribution centered in $\mu_t(s)$ and with $\sigma^2 = 1$ (independent samples over space), and the other one with $Y \sim GP(\mu, \Sigma)$, where Σ is generated using an exponential covariance function with range 8 and variance 2.

Following the procedures outlined above, we generate $B = 80$ data sets in each of six settings, 3 assuming independence for Y and 3 assuming a spatial covariance for Y , as described in Table 2.

We test the performance of five assumed models under six different data settings. The two models we consider are different versions of our model (**Model 1** and **Model 2**) using two options to model the covariance of Y and with and without incorporating the weights. Also, we compare the results to the full Bayesian model described in Section 3 to compare the performance in terms of running time and how well it estimates the coefficients.

- **Model 1:** Fast Emulator assuming independence over Y s.

- (a) Assuming all $v_k(s) = 1$.
- (b) Assuming $v_k(s)$ as a smooth surface, pre-estimated.

- **Model 2:** Fast Emulator modeling the covariance of Y .

- (a) Assuming all $v_k(s) = 1$.
- (b) Assuming $v_k(s)$ as a smooth surface, pre-estimated.
- (c) Assuming $v_k(s)$ as a smooth surface.

For Models 1b and 2b we pre-estimate $v_k(s)$ to plug it into the Bayesian model, and for model 2c we include posterior sampling of $v_k(s)$ using a fixed exponential covariance. We use 10000 MCMC iterations, with a burn in period of 3000 and we thin the sample every 5 iterations. We compute posterior medians and credible intervals, mean standard error (MSE), median absolute deviation (MAD) and coverage for each set of coefficients and average them over covariates, space, and iterations. For a particular model and setting MAD is computed in the following way, for each setting and model:

$$\text{MAD} = \text{Median}_{i \in \{1, N\}, b \in \{1, B\}, k \in \{1, p\}} |\hat{\beta}_k^b(s_i) - \beta_k^b(s_i)| \quad (9)$$

where $B = 80$ data sets and $N = 100$ locations. For MSE and coverage the mean is also computed over data sets, locations and covariates.

Tables 3, 4 and 5 present MSE, MAD, and mean coverage for each set of covariates, according to the settings used to generate the data and the models assumed to estimate it. Values were compared using the empirical standard error and credible intervals. The MSE and MAD for the coefficients when assuming Model 2a and 2b are statistically smaller in all of the settings generated with correlated Y s, compared to those from Model 1a and 1b. When comparing results for models using pre-estimated weights for β (1b and 2b) versus those that do not, Setting 2 and 5 (chessboard with and without correlated Y s) have a statistically significant improvement in both MSE and MAD. Models that take the weights into account have up to a 60% decrease of MAD for β relative to those that assume constant $v_s(k)$. Nevertheless, this difference is not reflected when comparing results for data generated with smooth weights and correlated Y when we do not model the variance of Y as spatial (setting 6 with 1a and 1b). This means that the fast emulator performs better or the same than the model that does not take into account the weights for β , for data generated using chessboard-like, smooth weights or not using weights, if we model the variance of Y using a spatial process.

Table 3. Average MSE for β and s.e in parenthesis, for each model and setting.

	M1a	M1b	M2a	M2b	M2c
Setting 1	0.178 (0.053)	0.179 (0.055)	0.397 (0.004)	0.397 (0.004)	0.831 (0.088)
Setting 2	0.623 (0.036)	0.382 (0.056)	0.655 (0.010)	0.439 (0.006)	1.449 (0.036)
Setting 3	0.341 (0.050)	0.312 (0.050)	1.127 (0.005)	1.154 (0.052)	1.186 (0.059)
Setting 4	0.328 (0.028)	0.331 (0.024)	0.100 (0.004)	0.100 (0.004)	0.859 (0.074)
Setting 5	1.655 (0.036)	0.505 (0.095)	0.427 (0.011)	0.191 (0.005)	1.471 (0.035)
Setting 6	1.207 (0.043)	1.207 (0.039)	0.143 (0.005)	0.035 (0.014)	1.478 (0.060)

Table 4. Average MAD for β and s.e in parenthesis, for each model and setting.

	M1a	M1b	M2a	M2b	M2c
Setting 1	0.284 (0.042)	0.286 (0.043)	0.415 (0.004)	0.414 (0.003)	0.669 (0.031)
Setting 2	0.603 (0.009)	0.391 (0.047)	0.856 (0.006)	0.458 (0.004)	0.897 (0.011)
Setting 3	0.438 (0.009)	0.402 (0.009)	0.558 (0.003)	0.558 (0.017)	0.565 (0.013)
Setting 4	0.490 (0.021)	0.487 (0.018)	0.211 (0.004)	0.211 (0.004)	0.673 (0.028)
Setting 5	0.856 (0.009)	0.415 (0.037)	0.502 (0.006)	0.295 (0.004)	0.899 (0.010)
Setting 6	0.559 (0.008)	0.560 (0.007)	0.209 (0.003)	0.098 (0.007)	0.738 (0.015)

Table 5. Average coverage for β and s.e in parenthesis, for each model and setting. Nominal level is 95%

	M1a	M1b	M2a	M2b	M2c
Setting 1	0.932 (0.012)	0.915 (0.011)	0.874 (0.007)	0.873 (0.006)	0.711 (0.010)
Setting 2	0.883 (0.003)	0.899 (0.008)	0.775 (0.008)	0.896 (0.006)	0.781 (0.011)
Setting 3	0.892 (0.006)	0.911 (0.003)	0.764 (0.006)	0.717 (0.007)	0.704 (0.008)
Setting 4	0.860 (0.008)	0.855 (0.007)	0.967 (0.006)	0.975 (0.006)	0.735 (0.012)
Setting 5	0.901 (0.001)	0.903 (0.007)	0.881 (0.005)	0.936 (0.006)	0.787 (0.011)
Setting 6	0.739 (0.003)	0.711 (0.003)	0.887 (0.008)	0.985 (0.008)	0.753 (0.012)

MAD and MSE results reflect the fact that our fast emulator benefits from using spatial correlation to get a better fit when there is spatial correlation in Y present, compared to the fit to independent Y s. Also, the use of pre-estimated weights benefit the fit of the model by 20% – 60% in cases where the data is generated using spatially varying weights. Therefore, when there is spatial correlation present in the data and the covariates' effect varies in space the simulation shows not only the need of a model that accounts for both the spatial correlation in the coefficients and in the response, but also how our approach to estimate these two levels of spatial dependency works better than the simpler model to estimate the coefficients.

Table 6. Time to run 10000 MCMC iterations per model, $N = 100$, $T = 12$.

Model	Time (minutes)
(1b) Independent Y / pre-estimate w	21.6
(2b) Exponential covariance Y / pre-estimate w	70.2
(2c) Exponential covariance Y / fix covariance w	84.1
(Full Bayesian) Exponential covariance Y / complete model	324.0

Model 2c performs poorly in all the cases. Although it is not significantly slower per iteration than model 2b in this simulation, there is evidence to prefer model 2b even though the error in v is not incorporated into the model. This might be due to the overparametrization of model 2c and also to the difficulties to make all the parameters converge in this case (see Figure 6). The fourth option presented in Table 6 is not feasible given its running times, thus we did not included it.

Figure 6. Trace plots for parameter σ^2 for (a) Model 2b and (b) Model 2c.

Furthermore, this simulation was done using $N = 100$ and, as we note in the next section, the computational cost for model 2c becomes a real burden when using $N=5200$ and in this case its benefits are not clear given its poor performance.

5 NARCCAP Data Analysis

In this section, the methodology from section 3 is applied to the data from section 2. The response in this case is precipitation (PR), and the final result is a high resolution climate map for the Western North American Region. In the application of interest, it is important to be able to (i) generate samples of the high resolution climate maps in a fast way (relative to the numerical models), and (ii) generate very similar variability patterns as in the original data set.

Feedback from the developers of NARCCAP data and some exploratory analysis allowed us to identify six input variables as primary determinants for precipitation, which in the notation of Section 3 translates into $P = 6$ and $T = 30$. We use $N = 5200$ locations in Western North America, described in Section 2.

For the purpose of showing the advantages of the proposed model, we apply and compare the results of the following emulators:

- (a) Full Bayesian model with fixed covariance structure for the weights (Model 2c).
- (b) Two Stage Bayesian model with spatially dependent errors (Model 2b).
- (c) Two Stage Bayesian model with spatially independent errors (Model 1b).
- (d) A Gaussian Process without spatially varying coefficients nor variable selection, i.e. $\beta_k(s) = \beta_k$.

The gaussian process model is used as a reference model, since it is the most common statistical emulator for computer output (Overstall and Woods (2016)). In each model, all parameters were estimated for the response PR by their marginal posterior medians from an MCMC sample of size

Table 7. Timing comparison for all models. Comparisons are done on a Dell Optiplex 9020 with a 3.60GHz Intel i7-4790 processor with 32GB RAM, and the code is written in the R programming language (R Core Team (2013)).

Data Set	Model 1b	Model 2b	Model 2c	Gaussian Model
N = 5200, T = 28 years Time to run 10000 MCMC	(J = 5,10,15) ~ 14 hours	(J = 5,10,15) ~ 22 hours	(J = 5,10,15) ~ 32 hours	~ 20 hours

10000. The number of MCMC iterations was determined using the lower bound for effective sample size with a Monte Carlo error of 0.05 and for a 95% credible region on the estimates, proposed by Vats et al. (2017). We discard the first 5000 as burn-in, and thin the chains by keeping every fifth iteration. We use the trace plots to check for convergence of all the parameters.

As part of our exploratory analysis, we ran several descriptive summaries to decide if it was necessary to include a temporal correlation structure for the response. The first summary per location we use is the ratio of the standard deviation of the residuals from two regression models with log precipitation as response and reference height temperature (TREFHT) as covariate: one with a lag 1 response as a covariate, and the other without the lagged term, to then obtain one ratio per each of the 5200 locations. The distribution of these ratios is centered in 1 and 50% of its values are between 0.990 and 1.018. Since the minimum value is 0.766 and the maximum is 1.020, the ratio does not present evidence of a lag 1 temporal component and thus we decide that including a temporal component does not improve our model. This temporal independence allows us to parallelize the approximation of the likelihood of Y in time for each MCMC iteration, which is an advantage in practice.

We evaluate the performance of in-sample and out-of-sample estimations for each of the emulators using likelihood scores. For the out-of-sample evaluation, we select the last 2 years from the original data set and construct the emulator using the other 28 years. For each of those 2 years, we save the true RCM outputs at the 5200 locations, and evaluate likelihoods of those observations using the four emulators, and with three different values for J for each of the three emulators that use basis functions (a,b,c), to evaluate the sensitivity (or the lack thereof) of the number of basis functions included in our emulators.

5.1 Results

The estimated time to run each of the models is presented in Table 7. Model 3b proves to be a computational burden when working with more than 5000 locations. Our results for this model are presented although they are not very meaningful, since the model did not converge with the same conditions as the other models.

We use mean squared error (MSE), median average deviation (MAD) and mean (negative) likelihood score (MLS) to

Table 8. In-sample results for all emulators using different values of J in the models that use basis decomposition representation. Standard errors are less than 0.02 for MSE, MAD and MLS.

	MSE(Y)	MAD(Y)	$Y \in CI$	MLS
Model 1b, $J = 5$	1.39	0.94	0.92	0.0621
Model 1b, $J = 10$	2.01	1.12	0.94	0.0689
Model 1b, $J = 20$	2.04	1.13	0.93	0.0695
Model 2b, $J = 5$	1.20	0.87	0.94	0.0365
Model 2b, $J = 10$	1.54	0.97	0.92	0.0378
Model 2b, $J = 20$	1.53	0.90	0.90	0.0381
Model 2c, $J = 5$	856.91	21.52	0.01	39.0274
Gaussian Model	2.44	1.34	1.00	0.1133

compare the performance of each of the four emulators when estimating the response. We define the likelihood score as:

$$MLS = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \frac{-\log p(y_t | \hat{\alpha}, \hat{\sigma}^2, \hat{\Omega})}{N}$$

where $\hat{\alpha}$, $\hat{\sigma}^2$, and $\hat{\Omega}$ are the estimated parameters. We use $t \in \{1, 28\}$ to construct the models when we have in-sample calculations and $t \in \{29, 30\}$ when we have out-of-sample calculations.

For all of them, smaller values represent good estimations. Also, we use the proportion of observations where the credible interval includes the observed value and labeled it as $Y \in CI$. The results in Table 8 and Table 9 show how models 1b and 2b have a significantly better performance compared to the Gaussian emulator and model 3b for both the in-sample and out-of-sample data sets, as expected. The Gaussian emulator does not include spatially varying coefficients, thus its estimations have very wide credible intervals compared to those of models 1b and 2b. This explains why the model presents 100% of observed values inside the credible interval for both in-sample and out-sample results, but a very poor MLS.

Different values for J were used for models 1b, 2b and 3b, to evaluate how sensitive the estimations are to the number of eigenfunctions used to estimate the coefficients. The in-sample and out-of-sample results show almost no difference when using $J = 10$ and $J = 20$, which is expected, given that the values of λ_j^2 for $j \geq 8$ are almost zero. The result is not the same for $J = 5$ which means that the model can be sensitive to having a number of eigenfunctions that is lower than the value of j for which λ_j^2 approaches zero. This could mean that if we use all the possible basis with $\lambda_j \neq 0$ we could be overfitting one or more coefficients..

Figure 7 contrasts RCM output values against corresponding predictions produced by each of the best emulators (1b and 2b), for a random sample of locations and years of the out-of-sample data set. For both emulators, the estimated (posterior median) output lies close to the true NARCCAP output, showing that they are emulating the true model quite accurately.

Table 9. Out-of-sample results for all emulators using different values of J in the models that use basis decomposition representation. Standard errors are less than 0.05 for MSE, MAD and MLS.

	MSE(Y)	MAD(Y)	$Y \in CI$	MLS
Model 1b, $J = 5$	1.36	0.93	0.92	0.8634
Model 1b, $J = 10$	1.94	1.10	0.95	0.9988
Model 1b, $J = 20$	2.05	1.21	0.96	1.0034
Model 2b, $J = 5$	1.06	0.81	0.89	0.8116
Model 2b, $J = 10$	1.84	1.08	0.92	0.8542
Model 2b, $J = 20$	1.95	1.15	0.91	0.8481
Model 2c, $J = 5$	858.71	21.54	0.01	1093.7231
Gaussian Model	2.29	1.29	1.00	2.9967

Figure 7. Comparison between model 1b and model 2b using a random sample of locations and places from the out-of-sample data set. Black dots represent posterior medians, and the lines represent the 95% credible intervals, for each model.

We choose to work with model 2b with $J = 5$ given its good performance for estimating the response in both in-sample and out-of-sample data sets. In terms of the interpretation, the most important parameter to interpret in this case is $v_k(s)$, since it can explain which covariates are the main drivers for RCM output and where. Temperature (TREFHT) is an important driver for summer precipitation in the northwestern and northern region of the United States, as it is the specific humidity (QBOT) but over the Pacific Ocean, in front of the West Coast of the U.S. From the jet level winds, the most important is U (East-West stream), that has a significant driver effect over the Rocky Mountains in the U.S. and in front of the Canadian west coast. Lastly, the vertical velocity shows evidence of being a good driver for summer precipitation in the western part of Canada.

Figure 8. Weights $v_k(s)$ for each covariate. Areas in white represent values not significantly different from zero, i.e. areas where the respective covariate does not represent a significant driver for summer precipitation.

6 Conclusions

This paper focuses on two objectives. First, we develop a statistical RCM emulator using GCM output, incorporating a spatial variable selection method to the Bayesian hierarchical model. Second, we consider the use of various versions of our emulator to model RCM output for summer precipitation in the Western part of the North American Region, using NARCCAP data. A discussion of the modeling advantages and restrictions implied by the four alternative emulators suggested that two stage Bayesian model with spatially dependent errors (Model 2b from Section 4) approach was the most satisfactory in terms of both variable selection and prediction performance. The full Bayesian model option presented several restrictions and no advantages, given its long running time and poor results.

Our approach proves to be computationally feasible and flexible enough to accommodate complex spatial structures. We show how using a small number of basis representations for each covariate can give the flexibility to the model to represent these complex spatial structures. Furthermore, we show how the use of data-dependent weights can facilitate the shrinkage of the resulting spatially varying coefficients, while keeping a feasible computing time for the model.

The evidence we present shows that the two stage emulator can form the basis for successful emulation of dynamic downscaling climate models, which in practice is an important tool for solving problems such as uncertainty analysis, sensitivity analysis and calibration of regional climate models. However, there remain some directions for further re-

search, such as the incorporation of a time structure in the response covariance in a computationally feasible way, in order to tackle the problem of monthly or daily emulation of RCMs.

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